

DATS 6103 Midterm Project

Breast Cancer Prediction

Main Objective

- 1. Load Data file from Data Source
- 2. Data processing and Cleanup.
- 3. Exploratory Data Analysis and Visualization.
- 4. Create Correlation Matrix and build model to predict whether breast cell tissue is malignant or Benign.

Project Description

The goal of this project is to examine the Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset and build the model to predict the cancer diagnosis is benign (or) malignant based on several observations and attributes from data file.

Data Source

- Using **Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Diagnostic) dataset** from the UCI Machine Learning Repository.
- The attributes I used in my data analysis are:
 - 1. Diagnosis - (M = malignant, B = benign)
 - 2. radius (mean of distances from center to points on the perimeter)
 - 3. texture (standard deviation of gray-scale values)
 - 4. perimeter
 - 5. area
 - 6. smoothness (local variation in radius lengths)
 - 7. compactness ($\text{perimeter}^2 / \text{area} - 1.0$)
 - 8. concavity (severity of concave portions of the contour)
 - 9. symmetry
 - 10. fractal dimension ("coastline approximation" - 1)

Data Processing and cleanup

- Checked for missing variables (`#data.isnull().any()`)
- Dropped unnamed and id columns. They are not useful for my analysis
- Attribute Diagnosis has two unique values (M = Malignant, B = Benign). I changed them to binary numbers. (0 for Benign and 1 for Malignant for easy data analysis)
- Created few smaller data frames to perform visualization for mean attributes from data file.
- Split data file into train(70%) and test datasets(30%) to build model to predict breast cancer.

EDA and Visualization

```
In [67]: #lets check data types
breast_cancer_data.dtypes
#all are numeric except 'diagnosis'. It's a object.
```

```
Out[67]: diagnosis                object
radius_mean                       float64
texture_mean                       float64
perimeter_mean                    float64
area_mean                         float64
smoothness_mean                   float64
compactness_mean                  float64
concavity_mean                    float64
concave points_mean               float64
symmetry_mean                     float64
fractal_dimension_mean            float64
radius_se                         float64
texture_se                        float64
perimeter_se                      float64
area_se                           float64
smoothness_se                    float64
compactness_se                   float64
concavity_se                      float64
concave points_se                 float64
symmetry_se                       float64
```

EDA and Visualization

```
In [65]: breast_cancer_data.head()
```

Out[65]:

	id	diagnosis	radius_mean	texture_mean	perimeter_mean	area_mean	smoothness_mean	compactness_mean	concavity_mean	concave points_mean	...	tex
0	842302	M	17.99	10.38	122.80	1001.0	0.11840	0.27760	0.3001	0.14710	...	
1	842517	M	20.57	17.77	132.90	1326.0	0.08474	0.07864	0.0869	0.07017	...	
2	84300903	M	19.69	21.25	130.00	1203.0	0.10960	0.15990	0.1974	0.12790	...	
3	84348301	M	11.42	20.38	77.58	386.1	0.14250	0.28390	0.2414	0.10520	...	
4	84358402	M	20.29	14.34	135.10	1297.0	0.10030	0.13280	0.1980	0.10430	...	

5 rows x 33 columns

Visualization

```
bc_data_mean=breast_cancer_data.iloc[:,1:11]
```

```
#Histogram form_mean columns from dataset  
bc_data_mean.hist(bins=50,figsize=(15,15))  
plt.show()
```

#Key Findings:

Attributes concavity, and concavity_point may have an exponential distribution
We see fractal_dimension, perimeter and radius mean have similiar distribution
We also see smOothness and symmetry mean have similar distribution.

area_mean

compactness_mean

concave points_mean

concavity_mean

fractal_dimension_mean

perimeter_mean

radius_mean

smoothness_mean

symmetry_mean

Visualization – Correlation Matrix


```
B1 : #Key Finding from correlation Matrix:  
# radius_mean, perimeter_mean and area_mean are highly correlated as we seen before from  
# histogram and denisity plot.  
# compactness_mean, concavity_mean and concavepoint_mean are highly correlated.
```

Split data into train and test to Build Model

```
In [87]: # Split data into train and test to Build Model
train_df, test_df = train_test_split(breast_cancer_data, test_size = 0.3)
labels = 'Train', 'Test'
plt.pie([70, 30], labels=labels, autopct='%1.1f%%', shadow=True)
plt.show()
print("Train set", train_df.shape)
print("Test set", test_df.shape)
```



```
Train set (398, 31)
Test set (171, 31)
```

Three Models

- Three methods I used for this classification problem and access the performance of each method are
- 1. Logistic Regression
- 2. KNN Model
- 3. SVM Model

Logistic Regression Model

```
# Logistic Regression model
predictor_var = ['texture_mean', 'perimeter_mean', 'smoothness_mean', 'compactness_mean', 'symmetry_mean']
outcome_var='diagnosis'
model=LogisticRegression()
classification_model(model,train_df,predictor_var,outcome_var)
```

Accuracy : 89.950%

Cross-Validation Score : 85.000%

Cross-Validation Score : 84.375%

Cross-Validation Score : 86.250%

Cross-Validation Score : 87.789%

Cross-Validation Score : 88.459%

K-Nearest Neighbors(KNN) Model

```
In [94]: #KNN Model
predictor_var = ['texture_mean', 'perimeter_mean', 'smoothness_mean', 'compactness_mean', 'symmetry_mean']
model= KNeighborsClassifier()
classification_model(model,train_df,predictor_var,outcome_var)
```

Accuracy : 93.719%

Cross-Validation Score : 92.500%

Cross-Validation Score : 89.375%

Cross-Validation Score : 90.417%

Cross-Validation Score : 89.964%

Cross-Validation Score : 89.693%

Support-Vector Machine(SVM) Model

```
In [95]: #SVM Model
predictor_var = ['texture_mean', 'perimeter_mean', 'smoothness_mean', 'compactness_mean', 'symmetry_mean']
model= SVC()
classification_model(model,train_df,predictor_var,outcome_var)
```

Accuracy : 93.467%

Cross-Validation Score : 82.500%

Cross-Validation Score : 82.500%

Cross-Validation Score : 85.417%

Cross-Validation Score : 85.265%

Cross-Validation Score : 85.174%

Key findings

- From correlation matrix we found that radius_mean, perimeter_mean and area_mean are highly correlated. We have seen the same in visualization part of histogram and density plot.
- Split data into train and test data and build three models(Logistic , KNN and SVM) for classification problem and access the performance of each method.
- Logistic Regression model Accuracy is 89.950%
- KNN Model Accuracy is 93.71%
- SVM Model Accuracy is 93.467%

Conclusions

```
# Logistic Regression model Accuracy is 89.950%
# KNN Model Accuracy is 93.71%
# SVM Model Accuracy is 93.467%
#
# Model                Accuracy (%)          Mean Cross-Validation Score (%)
# Logistic Regression    89.950                86.3746
# KNN Model              93.719                90.389
# SVM Model              93.467                84.171
```

- From the above result, KNN and SVM models(accuracy is 93.71% and 93.46%) would be chosen as the ideal models to analysis breast cancer diagnosis.
- Given breast tumor metrics, we would be better able to predict malignant versus benign diagnosis.

